

A NOTE ON CORCHORIN, A BITTER PRINCIPLE OF
CORCHORUS CAPSULARIS (JUTE SEEDS)

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Corchorin, a bitter principle of *Corchorus capsularis* (Jute seeds), which was isolated by Sen (this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 83) as almost colorless, rhombic prisms, m. p. 174-75°, has been described by him as a glucoside having the formula $C_{22}H_{36}O_8$; on hydrolysis Sen (*ibid*, 1930, 7, 905) obtained glucose and corchogenin, $C_{16}H_{26}O_9$, m. p. 113-14°.

As the structure of corchorin had not been definitely established, the problem was undertaken by us in July last. Since the method of isolation described by Sen (*loc. cit.*) appeared to be very cumbersome and lengthy, we have developed a much easier method of isolation leading to a better yield of corchorin. During our degradation experiments on corchorin we have come across a paper on "Constituents of the seeds of *Corchorus olitorius*, L." by Gabra Soliman and (in part) Wahba Saleh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2198) in which they have fully established the identity of corchorin with strophanthidin. Due to obvious delay in mails, this copy of the journal reached us only in November, 1950, and as such, further work in this line has been abandoned. As our method of isolation is different and much simpler and also gives much better yield, we communicate this for publication. The melting point of the acetyl derivative prepared by us, 242° (d) is the same as reported by these authors.

Isolation.—The seeds of *Corchorus capsularis* were finely crushed in a crusher and extracted in four batches of 500 g. each with benzene by cold percolation to remove the oil. The defatted seeds, thus obtained, were then exhaustively extracted with acetone in a large Soxhlet apparatus, the acetone was distilled off and the residue was taken up in water (3 litres), the aqueous solution treated with lead acetate and after removing the precipitated volamite and saponin, the excess of lead was removed by hydrogen sulphide and subsequent filtration. The red coloured filtrate on standing overnight deposited crystals of corchorin which were filtered off. Concentration of the mother-liquor to a small bulk (500 c.c.) on the water-bath gave a further crop of dirty white crystals of corchorin (total yield, 21.5 g.). On repeated crystallisation from dilute ethyl and methyl alcohols it was obtained as almost colorless rhombic prism, m. p. 174-75°, but traces of colouring matter persisted even on charcoal treatment. A very pure, colorless specimen, m. p. 177-78°, was, however, obtained by passing its alcoholic solution through a column of Brockmann alumina.

